

Yield of rice Rasi as influenced by coated urea materials. Andhra Pradesh, India, 1987 wet season.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)
Control	3.5
PU (standard split)	4.1
PU + new coating (basal)	4.8
LGU (basal)	5.3
LGU (standard split)	4.7
LGU + new coating (basal)	5.0
LGU + new coating (split)	5.1
USG placement, 7 DT	5.6
Neem cake-coated USG (7 DT)	5.9
New coating + USG (7 DT)	5.6
Experimental mean	5.0
LSD (0.05)	0.4
CV (%)	5.1

There was no significant grain yield difference among USG, neem cake-coated USG, and USG with the new coating. □

Effect of urea-based N sources in rice - wheat cropping sequence

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We compared 5 urea sources—prilled urea (PU), gypsum-coated urea (GCU), nitrohumic-coated urea (NHCU), urea supergranule (USG), and Mussoorie phos-coated urea (MPCU) — at 56, 84, and 112 kg N/ha in a 1986-87 wet season-winter season field experiment.

Soil was a clay loam with pH 7.3, 0.34% organic C, 9.7 kg available P/ha (NaHCO₃ extract), and 132.8 kg available K/ha (ammonium acetate extract). The experiment was in a split-plot design (N in the main plots and sources in the subplots) with three replications.

Seedlings of 150-d-duration rice variety Jaishree at 2/hill were transplanted on 19 Jul at 20- × 15-cm spacing. All plots received 17.2 kg P and 16.6 kg K/ha. All GCU (31% N), NHCU (46% N), USG (46% N), MPCU (32% N), and 1/3 PU were applied at transplanting. USG was placed 8 cm

deep in the center of 4 hills 10 d after transplanting (DT). Additional PU was applied in equal splits at 20 DT and at panicle initiation. The other N sources were incorporated at puddling.

The rice crop was harvested 20 Nov and the succeeding wheat crop, cultivar HP 1209, was sown 12 Dec. The wheat crop was fertilized with 50 kg N, 21.5 kg P, and 20.7 kg K/ha including the previous control plots. The wheat crop received three irrigations.

Rice grain yield increased significantly up to 112 kg N/ha because of increased panicles/m² and filled spikelets/panicle

(see table). Yields with USG were similar to those with PU and significantly greater than those with other N sources. The higher yield with USG was due mainly to larger panicles/m² and filled spikelets/panicle.

Residual effects of 84 and 112 kg N/ha were similar and significantly superior to those of 56 kg N/ha in the succeeding wheat crop (see table). Maximum wheat grain yield in the plot that received USG for the preceding rice was significantly superior to that with PU alone. □

Rice yield attributes, rice grain yield, and wheat grain yield with urea-based N sources. Bihar, India, 1986-87 wet-winter seasons.

Treatment	Panicles (no./m ²)	Filled spikelets/panicle	1000-grain wt (g)	Grain yield (t/ha)	
				Rice	Wheat
N (kg/ha)					
0	169	70.1	19.8	2.3	2.5
56	229	90.5	21.3	3.1	2.9
84	243	98.0	22.1	3.5	3.0
112	263	99.9	22.5	3.8	3.2
LSD (0.05)	7.6	2.3	0.2	0.1	0.2
Forms of urea					
PU	250	92.8	22.1	3.6	2.9
GCU	232	96.8	21.8	3.3	3.0
NHCU	241	95.6	21.9	3.5	3.0
USG	261	100.6	21.2	3.8	3.2
MPCU	244	94.8	22.0	3.2	3.1
LSD (0.05)	6.9	2.4	ns	0.2	0.2

Effect of N source and application method on dry season irrigated rice

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We studied timing of urea application and method of urea supergranules (USG) placement on a clay loam soil with pH 6.5, 0.07% total N, 20 ppm available P, and 0.2 meq exchangeable K/100 g soil. Treatments are given in the table.

N was applied at 58 kg/ha. Urea was

Effect of N source and method of application on performance of BR3 at BRRI. ^a Bangladesh.

Treatment ^b	Panicles (no./m ²)	Grain yield (t/ha)	N efficiency (kg grain/kg N)	N recovery (%)
No N	202	f	3.31	d
Urea 1/2 basal + 1/2 MT	222	e	4.31	c
Urea 1/3 basal + 1/3 IT + 1/3 5-7 DBPI	244	d	4.54	c
Urea 1/3 IT + 1/3 RT + 1/3 5-7 DBPI	252	c	4.63	c
USG deep placed with open hole	298	b	5.31	ab
USG deep placed with closed hole	305	a	5.49	a
CV (%)	7.4	4.4		

^aIn a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level of DMRT. ^bExcept for no N, N for all treatments is 58 kg/ha. MT = maximum tillering, IT = initial tillering, RT = rapid tillering, DBPI = days before panicle initiation.